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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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THE RESPONSIBILITIES AND SANCTIONS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW DURING ARMED CONFLICT: A CASE STUDY OF RUSSIA AND UKRAINE WAR

By
Ibrahim Danjuma*

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13855534

ABSTRACT

International Law has long served as the governing framework for State conduct on the global stage, extending its regulatory reach even to periods of armed conflict involving States and non-State actors. Within this complex arena, International Humanitarian Law assumes a critical role, meticulously overseeing the behavior of belligerent States and non-State entities, particularly in their treatment towards sick, wounded soldiers, prisoners of war, as well as other vulnerable groups that are not engaged in hostilities. However, the persistence of numerous ongoing conflicts worldwide prompts a probing of the effectiveness of International Humanitarian Law in armed conflicts. The Russia-Ukraine war is a poignant case study within this broader context. This research delves into the examination of States' responsibilities and the enforcement mechanisms delineated in International Humanitarian Treaties, specifically scrutinizing their application in the tumultuous theatre of the Russia-Ukraine conflict. Adopting a Doctrinal legal research approach, this study reveals that there are discernible infractions of International Humanitarian Law in the course of the Russia-Ukraine conflict. Despite the imposition of sanctions by certain States, a critical evaluation suggests that these measures fell short of delivering the desired impact in compelling compliance with pertinent international humanitarian norms.

Keywords: *Armed Conflict, Russia, Ukraine, International Law, International Humanitarian Law, LOAC.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Notwithstanding the developments in International Humanitarian Law (IHL), especially the enactment of Conventions and protocols to address Humanitarian crises globally, significant changes were not recorded in terms of curtailment and mitigation of wars for it was after the Geneva Conventions, that the world witnessed the World War I (1914-1918)¹; World War II (1939-1945)²; Korean War (1950-1953)³; Vietnam War (1954-1975)⁴; Gulf War (1990-1991); Syrian Civil War (2011-present)⁵ and recently, the Russia and Ukraine War. It was recorded that since the World War II, there has not been a year (including post 2000s) that have not witnessed a war with at least 100,000 people killed.⁶

The conflict between Russia and Ukraine has been one of the most serious and complex crises in Europe since the end of the Cold War. It began in 2014 with the annexation of Crimea by Russia and the outbreak of a Pro-Russian Separatist Rebellion in Eastern Ukraine, and escalated in 2022-2023 with a full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine that sparked international condemnation and sanctions.⁷ The conflict has resulted in thousands of deaths, millions of displaced people, and widespread violations of human rights and IHL.

The concepts and practices of international law have faced complicated and multidimensional test over time and recently by the armed war between Russia and Ukraine, which started in 2014. The persistent offensive military operations, territorial disputes, and allegations of human rights and humanitarian violations that have

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¹ Dennis E Showalter and Royde-Smith, John Graham, "World War I". (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/World-War-I>> Accessed 4 October 2023.

² Thomas A Hughes and Royde-Smith, John Graham, "World War II" (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/World-War-II>> Accessed 4 October 2023.

³ Allan R Millett, "Korean War" (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Korean-War>> Accessed 4 October 2023.

⁴ Ronald H Spector, "Vietnam War" (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Vietnam-War>> Accessed 4 October 2023.

⁵ The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, "Syrian Civil War" (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Syrian-Civil-War>> Accessed 4 October 2023

⁶ Khan Academy, "Conflicts Between Countries Since 1945" <www.khanacademy.org/humanities/whp-origins/era-7-the-great-convergence-and-divergence-1880-ce-to-the-future/x23c41635548726c4:other-materials-origins-era-7/a/conflicts-between-countries-since-1945>

⁷ Ukraine conflict: Your guide to understanding the story. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-europe-60513807> Accessed on 25th September 2023

characterized this conflict for so long have called into serious question the ability of international law to confront and resolve such conflicts. The purpose of this study is to examine the obligations and penalties set forth by international law in the context of armed conflicts and to evaluate their application—or lack thereof—in the instance of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine.

Using a doctrinal approach, the scope of this research paper encompasses an in-depth analysis of the responsibilities and sanctions associated with international humanitarian treaties, focusing specifically on the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. The study aims to examine the legal framework established by the IHL and its application in the context of the aforementioned conflict. In order to accomplish the above tasks, this study begins with an overview of International Law during armed conflict; examines the concept of IHL; identifies the treatise applicable to an armed conflict; highlights the responsibilities of States under International Law; discusses the inter-State conflict between Russia and Ukraine; identifies the sanctions to be imposed for violation of IHL; findings and conclusion.

2. BACKGROUND ON INTERNATIONAL LAW IN ARMED CONFLICTS

The concept of international law is attributed to many definitions often formulated from two points of view which are: philosophical and scientific. The former sees international law as it ought to be while the latter sees it as it is generally observed in interstate relationship.

Bentham defined international law as “a collection of rules governing relations between states”. Similarly, it was defined by Shaw as “the body of legal rules, norms, and standards that apply between sovereign states and other entities that are legally recognized as international actors”.⁸

Wheaton,⁹ defined International law “as consisting of those rules of conduct which reason deduces, as consonant to justice, from the nature of the society existing among independent nations; with such definitions and modifications as may be established by general consent.”

⁸ Malcolm N Shaw, *International Law* (8th Edn, Cambridge University Press 2008). <<https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511841637>>

⁹ Henry Wheaton, “*Elements of international law*” (8th ed, Sampson Low, Son & Co. 1866) <https://openlibrary.org/books/OL16755947M/Elements_of_international_law>

This definition emphasizes the customary and consensual nature of international law, derived from the practices, customs, and consent of nations in the international community. It also underscores the idea that international law is based on principles of justice and the relationships between sovereign states.

Legal Scholars including Bynkersheok, Puffendorf, Wolf and Battel, just like Wheaton, have argued that International Law is derived from reason, customs and usages rather than an established law making body. Perhaps, if a law making body would exist in the international scene, it would be persuasive rather than coercive to the states. To that end, Bynkersheok says,

“the law of nations is that which is observed in accordance with the light of reason, between nations, if not among all, at least certainly among the greater part, and those the most civilized.”¹⁰

He further added:

"Reason commands me to be equally friendly to two of my friends who are enemies to each other; and hence it follows that I am not to prefer either in war. Usage is shown by the constant, and, as it were, perpetual custom which sovereigns have observed of making treaties and ordinances upon this subject, for they have often made such regulations by treaties to be carried into effect in case of war, and by laws enacted after the commencement of hostilities. I have said by, as it were, a perpetual custom; because one, or perhaps two treaties, which vary from the general usage, do not alter the law of nations."¹¹

International Law is broadly divided into two: Private International Law and Public International Law. The former according to Malcom¹² “deals with those cases, within particular legal systems, in which foreign elements obtrude, raising questions as to the application of foreign law or the role of foreign courts” while the latter “covers relations between states in all their myriad forms”. For the purpose of this research, a reference

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Malcolm N Shaw, *International Law* (8th Edn, Cambridge University Press 2008). <<https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511841637>>

to International law is restricted to Public International law as it is the category that will best address the research problem.

The Scope of International Law at the early stage of its formulation as a concept is restricted to inter-relations between States. It poses an irony that states are both the subject and object of International law. On the one hand, the states make international laws through their customs and treaties while International Law on the other hand defines what a state is. As D'Amato puts it:

“Even the most basic player in international law, namely the state, is defined by international law. We know an entity is a state when international law tells us it is a state. In short, if a new state calls itself a state, it is, in fact, scanning the panorama of legal rules that tell us what a state is. If the facts comport with its assertions, the new state is close to achieving statehood”.¹³

However, recent developments in the field have recognized Individuals and International Organizations (commonly called international actors) as subjects of International law.¹⁴ Individuals were formally recognized by International law with the evolution of Human Rights which was seen as a universal concern. States have since engaged in multi-lateral and bi-lateral agreements for the purpose of protecting and promoting the individuals from human rights violations. The rights of individuals under international law are detailed in various human rights instruments and agreements. Although references to the protection of human rights appear in the UN Charter, the principal engine of the process was the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948; UDHR).¹⁵

2.1 ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN ARMED CONFLICT

¹³ Anthony D'Amato, “International Law as a Unitary System” (Northwestern Public Law Research Paper No. 08-02 2008) <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=1106420>> or <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1106420>>

¹⁴ Malcolm N Shaw, International Law (8th Edn, Cambridge University Press 2008). <<https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511841637>> Accessed 5 October 2023

¹⁵ Malcolm Shaw, “international law” (Encyclopedia Britannica 2023) <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/international-law>> Accessed 5 October 2023

International law in the context of armed conflicts bears different pseudo including laws of war, Laws of Armed Conflict (LOAC) and International Humanitarian Law. All of those connotations though are used interchangeably.

As a branch of law that regulates the conduct of states towards one another, International law plays a crucial role in the Armed Conflict in two general ways i.e. Spelling who has the right to use force and the way and manner the force should be used. These are popularly referred to as Jus Ad Bellum and Jus in Bello.

Jus Ad Bellum is a Latin phrase which means ‘the right to resort to force’ or ‘the right to wage war’. Its scope revolves around who may use force in international relations and in what circumstances may he or she use such force.¹⁶ Until 1945, States are at liberty to use force on another state as a matter of discretion. However, the Charter of the United Nations laid the foundation for Jus Ad Bellum by limiting that power on the states thereby affirming the sovereignty of the states once more. Article 2 of the Charter provides thus:

“All members shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or the use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state, or in any other manner inconsistent with the purposes of the United Nations”

Notwithstanding, the UN Charter still vest the right to use force on the state but subject to requirements and limitations among which is the right of self-defence enshrined in Article 51 of the UN Charter.

Within the UN structure, the Security Council functions as a sort of guardian of international peace and security. The scope of it allowed action which is not limited to collective security in the narrow sense and therefore extend beyond a reaction by all members against an aggressor. The role of the Council extends to a collective responsibility for world peace in the broad sense and has been broadened to encompass what are today often called ‘human security’ issues.

When a conflict starts, the principles of *jus in bello* or justice in war, provide a framework for effective combat. It thus follows that the agents of war must answer for

¹⁶ Kolb, R., & Hyde, R. (2008). An Introduction to the International Law of Armed Conflicts. In *Tilburg law review* (Issue 4, p. 486). Hart Publishing. <http://www.derechoshumanos.unlp.edu.ar/assets/files/documentos/an-introduction-to-the-international-law-of-armed-conflicts.pdf>

their deeds in accordance with *jus in bello*. Soldiers commit murder rather than acts of war when they kill civilians, pursue their adversary beyond what is reasonable, or break other morally-responsible regulations. The two overarching concepts of discrimination and proportionality comprise the rules of just conduct during times of conflict. While the principle of proportionality deals with the amount of force that is morally acceptable, the principle of discriminating deals with who is a lawful target in conflict. To the conventional two, there is a third principle that might be added: the principle of responsibility, which calls for an analysis of where responsibility lies in a war.

2.2 THE CONCEPT OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW

The Concept of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) has received varieties of definitions from Scholars and International Humanitarian Organisations like the International Committee of Red Cross.

According to Jean-Marie Henckaerts,¹⁷ IHL is also known as "the international law of armed conflict, or simply the law of armed conflict (LOAC) or law of war" or with its Latin name *Jus In Bello* (law applicable in armed conflict). The rules of International Humanitarian Law seek to limit the effects of armed conflict and at its core, aims to preserve a sense of humanity in time of war.

According to Crowe, J., & Weston-Scheuber, K.,¹⁸ IHL is "the body of international law governing the conduct of armed conflicts". This definition is anchored on the philosophy that International Humanitarian Law places limits on the conduct of armed conflicts due to what the authors call the morally exceptional nature of warfare.

According to the International Committee of the Red Cross, "International humanitarian law (IHL) is a set of rules that seeks, for humanitarian reasons, to limit the effects of armed conflict. It protects persons who are not, or are no longer, directly

¹⁷ Jean-Marie Henckaerts, "History and Sources" In Ben Saul and Dapo Akande (Eds.), *The Oxford Guide to International Humanitarian Law* (Oxford University Press 2020)

¹⁸ Jonathan Crowe and Kylie Weston-Scheuber, "Principles of International Humanitarian Law." (Edward Elgar Publishing 2015) <www.e-elgar.com/shop/gbp/principles-of-international-humanitarian-law-9781782545941.html>

or actively participating in hostilities, and imposes limits on the means and methods of warfare."¹⁹

A similar definition of the Concept was given by the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations to mean "a set of rules that seek to limit the effects of armed conflict. It lays out the responsibilities of states and non-state armed groups during an armed conflict".²⁰

According to Gary D. Solis, IHL refers to the body of treaty-based and customary international law aimed at protecting the individual in time of international or non-international armed conflict – treaties, for example, such as 1949 Geneva Convention IV, for the protection of civilians.²¹

Modern International Humanitarian Law could be traced to the 1800s when the Battle of Solferino took place. Henry Dunant, a Swiss businessman having witnessed the war and the suffering it has inflicted on the people found the Red Cross Movement. The Red Cross movement, which is now considered 'a promoter and custodian of the humanitarian idea and the primary initiation for its transition into international humanitarian law'²², instigated the adoption in 1864 of the Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field.

2.3 TREATISE REGULATING ARMED CONFLICTS

The followings are the treatises regulating armed conflicts and thus:

2.3.1 THE GENEVA CONVENTIONS

Sir Henry Dunant after witnessing the Battle of Solferino made two suggestions in his book, "A Memory of Solferino". One of the suggestions is that state should conclude a treaty that would facilitate the activities of relief societies and guarantee a better treatment of the wounded. A year later, a committee named the International

¹⁹ International Committee of the Red Cross, "What is international humanitarian law?" (International Committee of the Red Cross 2022) <<https://www.icrc.org/en/document/what-international-humanitarian-law>>

²⁰ European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations, "International Humanitarian Law" <https://civil-protection-humanitarian-aid.ec.europa.eu/what/humanitarian-aid/international-humanitarian-law_en>

²¹ Gary D. Solis, "The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law at War" (Cambridge University Press 2010)

²² Michael A. Meyer and Hilaire McCoubrey (eds), "Reflections on Law and Armed Conflicts: The Selected Works on the Laws of War by the Late Professor Colonel G.I.A.D Draper" (1998), 69. Cited by Amanda Alexander, "A Short History of International Humanitarian Law" (European Journal of International Law Volume 26 Issue 1 2015) 109–138 <<https://doi.org/10.1093/ejil/chv002>>

Committee for the Relief of Military Wounded was created in response to the Dunant's recommendation. The committee was able to convince the Swiss Government to convene the first conference of parties that adopted the Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded in Armies in the Field in 1864.²³

As time goes on, the need for a revision of the Geneva Convention presented itself. Thus in 1906, thirty-five states who were parties to the 1864 Geneva Conventions met at Geneva and a Revised version of the 1864 Convention was birthed containing thirty-three articles.

After the World War I which is the biggest war the world has ever seen at that time containing 65,000,000 soldiers around the world, prisoners of war were too numerous to count. This has presented a challenge to the International Humanitarian Aid groups and all current Conventions and codes including The Hague Regulations on Prisoners of War. This prompted another Convention convened by the International Committee of Red Cross at Geneva. The output of the Conference was the adoption of the Geneva Convention of 1929 which supplemented the 1864 Geneva Convention and The Hague Regulations on Prisoners of War. At the same Convention, the 1906 Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick was amended and strengthened.²⁴

Among other things, the Convention addressed the following issues; the conditions in which prisoners should be captured and evacuated; the organization of camps; food and clothing for prisoners; hygiene; religious practice; mental and physical recreation; discipline inside camps; prisoners 'financial resources; prison labour; prisoners' mail, including parcels; penal sanctions concerning prisoners of war, and legal proceedings; the repatriation of prisoners of war.²⁵The Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949 are made up of four international treaties, ratified or acceded to by virtually all States.²⁶

²³ Muhammad Islam, "The Historical Evolution of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) from Earliest Societies to Modern Age" (Beijing Law Review 2018) 9, 294-307 <<https://doi.org/10.4236/blr.2018.92019>>

²⁴ Gary D Solis, "The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law IN WAR" (2010) 97.

²⁵ ICRC, "Geneva Convention of 27 July 1929 relative to the treatment of prisoners of war" <<https://www.icrc.org/en/doc/resources/documents/misc/57jnws.htm>>

²⁶ ICRC, "The Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949" (International Committee of the Red Cross 2021) <<https://www.icrc.org/en/publication/0173-geneva-conventions-august-12-1949>>

The First Convention also referred to "GC I" or "GCW" is formally called the Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field of August 12, 1949. It is a derivative and an expansion of the 1929 Convention on the same subject. As its name implies, the Convention is dedicated to providing protection for the wounded and sick and also for medical and religious personnel, medical units and medical transports.²⁷

The Second Geneva Convention formally called the Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of the Armed Forces at Sea of August, 1949 is also relating to the wounded and the sick. But unlike the First Convention, this one relates to the forces at sea. It is also referred to as the "GC II" or "GCWSea".²⁸

The Third Convention, the Geneva Convention Relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War replaced the 1929 Geneva Convention on the Treatment of Prisoners of War. It is abbreviated as "GC III" or "GPW". The Convention which is drafted in 143 articles have covered areas like the conditions and prison facilities of prisoners, the labour of prisoners of war, their financial resources, the relief they receive and the judicial proceedings instituted against them all of which were not clearly treated under the 1929 Convention.²⁹

The fourth convention is the Geneva Convention Relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, "GC IV". International Humanitarian Treatises are always a response to one form of war or another. Similarly, the Fourth Geneva Convention was adopted as a response to the German Occupation of the Europe and the Holocaust.³⁰

Dapper, while sharing the innovations of the Fourth Geneva Convention remarked thus:

²⁷ ICRC, "Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries, Convention (I) for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field" (Geneva, 1949) <<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/gci-1949?activeTab=1949GCs-APs-and-commentaries>> Last accessed on 21.06.2023

²⁸ Solis, G. D. (2010). *The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law at War*. Cambridge University Press.

²⁹ ICRC Database, *Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries, Convention (III) relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War*. Geneva, 12 August 1949., <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/gcii-1949?activeTab=1949GCs-APs-and-commentaries> (Last accessed on 21.06.2023)

³⁰ L. C. Green, "Grave Breaches' or Crimes Against Humanity," 8 *J. of Legal Studies* (1997–1998), 19, 21. cited by Solis, G. D. (2010). *The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law at War*. Cambridge University Press.

“Now civilians, whenever they are in the hands of the enemy power, have a detailed protection that can be supervised by the Protecting Power and the International Committee of the Red Cross, and enforced by direct penal action against those, whether they be private individuals or officials, who violate that protection in a grave manner. This Civilian’s Convention was called into being by the civilized States of the community of nations as a direct result of the experience of the Second World War.³¹

More Explanation on the Scope and application of these Conventions

2.3.2 ADDITIONAL PROTOCOLS TO THE GENEVA CONVENTION

The Additional Protocols to the Geneva Convention supplement the 1949 Conventions, rather than replace any portion of them. They supplement the Conventions by extending the scope of their application, the categories of protected persons and objects and the protection conferred. Today, additional protocols have become as much relevant as the 1949 Conventions themselves.

i. 1977 Additional Protocol I

The Additional Protocols I formally known as the 1977 Geneva Protocol I Additional to the Geneva Conventions of 12 August 1949, and Relating to the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts, is the first of the additional protocols which is specifically targeted at the protection of Victims of International Conflicts.

The Nine One Article Protocol has been exceptional in reducing a bulk of Customary Humanitarian Laws into the treaty. However, this was not possible without the stiff opposition of the western powers especially the United States. Under the Protocol, additional acts were added to what would amount a breach of the protocol. They include: apartheid, delayed prisoner of war (POW) repatriation, attacking some protected objects, transfers or deportations of certain people to or from occupied territory, and depriving protected persons of a fair and regular trial.

ii. 1977 ADDITIONAL PROTOCOLS II

³¹ G.I.A.D. Draper, “The Historical Background and General Principles of the Geneva Conventions of 1949,” in Michael A. Meyer and Hilaire McCoubrey, eds., *Reflections on Law and Armed Conflict* (The Hague: Kluwer Law International, 1998), 60. Cited by Solis, G. D. (2010). *The Law of Armed Conflict: International Humanitarian Law at War*. Cambridge University Press.

Additional Protocol II was the first-ever international treaty devoted exclusively to protecting people affected by non-international armed conflicts, or civil wars.³² Like the Additional Protocols I, the Additional Protocols II has achieved the codification of most Humanitarian rules that were regarded customary. Provisions worthy of note includes there are provisions worthy of note includes humanitarian protections of common Article 3, provisions for the protection of civilians from attack, as well as adding protection for objects indispensable to the survival of the civilian population. Lastly, it provides requirements for the care of children, including education, and a ban on the recruitment or participation in hostilities of persons under ages fifteen.

i. 2005 ADDITIONAL PROTOCOL III

The background that led to the adoption of the 2005 Additional Protocols is the clamour by many state to opt for a protective emblem of their choice rather than the widely known Red Cross on a white background adopted in October 1863 meeting of the International Standing Committee for Aid to Wounded Soldiers.

The first country to raise that issue was Turkey during the Russo-Turkish War (1876–1878). Turkey attributed a religious significance to the Red Cross and, in a fait accompli, informed the Swiss depository of the first Geneva Convention that, although Turkey would respect the Red Cross, its own forces would use a red crescent as the protective sign.

As soon as the Turkish dissent, countries like Persia (Now Iran), Israel, India, Sudan and a host of others also clamoured for a distinct sign on their emblem.

In December, 2005, Switzerland convened another conference where it adopted the Red Crescent proposed by Turkey and adding a new, third, neutrality emblem, “the red crystal.” The red crystal is a red, four-sided, diamond-shaped sign with thick borders. A state opting to adopt the red crystal may add its own smaller emblem to the interior of the open diamond. Thus, Israel will add the red Shield of David’s six-pointed star. India will add a cart wheel, Syria, a red palm and Sudan, a Rhinoceros.

More Explanation on the Scope and application of these Additional Protocols

³² ICRC, “Protocols I and II additional to the Geneva Conventions” <[241](https://www.icrc.org/en/doc/resources/documents/misc/additional-protocols-1977.htm#:~:text=Additional%20Protocol%20I%20lays%20down%20rules%20on%20the,injury%20to%20civilians%20and%20damage%20to%20civilian%20objects.></p>
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3. RESPONSIBILITIES OF STATES UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAW

The idea of responsibility is crucial to the application and observance of the law. A right is typically accompanied by a corresponding duty. The person who violates this commitment may be held liable for any civil or criminal obligations that result from that action. Individual accountability is common, particularly in international criminal law. Representatives of states enjoy jurisdictional immunity, with the exception of cases involving genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. States are subject to a unique set of obligations when another State violates its international obligations. The State's accountability is triggered by the actions of its agents, particularly its armed forces, as well as by people or organizations that act in reality under its actual supervision (see below). The International Court of Justice has the authority to look into certain circumstances and order States to make restitution.³³

State responsibility for failing to respect obligations under IHL can be triggered in front of the International Court of Justice by other governments suffering damages related to such violations and can lead to compensation. State failure to prosecute perpetrators of war crimes, crimes against humanity, and genocide at the national level may in certain circumstances trigger the competence of the International Criminal Court. Indeed, the Court's jurisdiction over a situation is established by the State ratification of the ICC Statute or by a binding decision of the United Nations Security Council, when this State is unwilling or unable to prosecute alleged offenders.³⁴

States party to the Geneva Conventions “undertake to respect and to ensure respect for the Geneva Conventions in all circumstances.”³⁵ This general commitment translates into several concrete responsibilities:

States are under the obligation to disseminate the text of humanitarian law conventions widely among their armed forces and civilians.³⁶ For instance, they should include the rules and regulations of humanitarian law in their military regulations,

³³ *Doctors Without Borders “The Practical Guide to Humanitarian Law”* <<https://guide-humanitarian-law.org/content/article/3/responsibility/>>

³⁴ Art. 17 of ICC Statute

³⁵ GCI-IV Art. 1; API Arts. 1, 80.2

³⁶ GCI Art. 47; GCII Art. 48; GCIII Art. 127; GCIV Art. 144; API Arts. 83.1, 87.2; and APII Art. 19

instructions for armed forces, and code of military discipline, and they must ensure that their commanders know the rules. Political and military authorities have the obligation to take all necessary measures to ensure that the obligations foreseen by humanitarian law are respected.³⁷

States are under the obligation to enact any legislation necessary to provide effective criminal sanctions for persons committing, or ordering to be committed, any of the grave breaches.³⁸ States are under the obligation to search for persons alleged to have committed, or to have ordered to be committed, such grave breaches, and shall bring such persons before their own courts.³⁹ This is regardless of the nationality of the accused, who may be a member of their own armed forces.

States are responsible for all acts committed by members of their armed forces. Furthermore, if a State violates humanitarian law, it may be held accountable and be compelled to pay compensation.⁴⁰ A State may not absolve itself or any other State of any liability incurred with regard to breaches of the Geneva Conventions committed by their authorities, their nationals, or in their name.⁴¹

These treaty provisions of State responsibility are confirmed by the customary IHL study published by the ICRC in 2005. Rules of customary humanitarian law draw the following obligations that rest on States in connection with their actions in international and non-international armed conflicts:

A State is responsible for violations of international humanitarian law attributable to it, including:

- I. Violations committed by its organs, including its armed forces;
- II. Violations committed by persons or entities it empowered to exercise elements of governmental authority;
- III. Violations committed by persons or groups acting in fact on its instructions, or under its direction or control; and

³⁷ GCI Art. 49; GCII Art. 50; GCIII Art. 129; GCIV Art. 146; and API Arts. 80.1, 86, and 87

³⁸ GCI Art. 49, GCII Art. 50, GCIII Art. 129, and GCIV Art. 146

³⁹ GCI Art. 49, GCII Art. 50, GCIII Art. 129, GCIV Art. 146, and API Art. 86

⁴⁰ API Art. 91

⁴¹ GCI Art. 51, GCII Art. 52, GCIII Art. 131, and GCIV Art. 148

- IV. Violations committed by private persons or groups that it acknowledges and adopts as its own conduct.⁴²
- V. A State responsible for violations of international humanitarian law in the context of an international or a non-international armed conflict is required to make full reparation for the loss or injury caused.⁴³
- VI. States must investigate war crimes allegedly committed by their nationals or armed forces, or on their territory, and, if appropriate, prosecute the suspects. They must also investigate other war crimes over which they have jurisdiction and, if appropriate, prosecute the suspects.⁴⁴
- VII. Finally, States must make every effort to cooperate, to the extent possible, with each other in order to facilitate the investigation of war crimes and the prosecution of the suspects.⁴⁵

4. CASE STUDY: CONFLICT BETWEEN RUSSIA AND UKRAINE

The conflict between Russia and Ukraine has been one of the most serious and complex crises in Europe since the end of the Cold War. It began in 2014 with the annexation of Crimea by Russia and the outbreak of a pro-Russian separatist rebellion in eastern Ukraine, and escalated in 2022-2023 with a full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine that sparked international condemnation and sanctions.⁴⁶ The conflict has resulted in thousands of deaths, millions of displaced people, and widespread violations of human rights and international humanitarian law (IHL).

The main causes of the Russia and Ukraine crisis are discussed below:

1. Historical and cultural ties: Ukraine has a long and complicated history with Russia, dating back to the medieval times when both countries were part of the Kievan Rus State. Ukraine's position between Russia to the east and countries such as Poland and Romania to the west means it straddles both the European

⁴² Rule 149

⁴³ Rule 150

⁴⁴ Rule 158

⁴⁵ Rule 161

⁴⁶ Ukraine conflict: Your guide to understanding the story. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-europe-60513807> Accessed on 25th September 2023

and Russian spheres of influence.⁴⁷ This is a major reason why tensions are so high. Russia has long resisted Ukraine's move towards the European Union, seeing it as a threat to its own interests and security.

2. Political and economic instability: Ukraine's political system has been plagued by corruption, oligarchy, and weak institutions since its independence in 1991. The country has also faced economic challenges, such as high inflation, low growth, and dependence on Russian gas. These factors have fuelled public discontent and social unrest, leading to several popular uprisings and changes of government. The most recent one was in 2014, when protesters ousted Ukraine's pro-Russian president Viktor Yanukovich in the Revolution of Dignity.⁴⁸ This triggered a backlash from Moscow, which feared losing its influence over Kyiv.
3. Crimea annexation: In February 2014, shortly after Yanukovich's ouster, Russia covertly invaded and annexed the Ukrainian autonomous republic of Crimea, a strategic peninsula on the Black Sea that hosts a large Russian naval base. Russia claimed that it was protecting the rights of the ethnic Russian majority in Crimea, who voted in a disputed referendum to join Russia. However, the international community condemned the move as a violation of Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity.⁴⁹ The annexation sparked a wave of sanctions against Russia from the West, as well as a diplomatic crisis.
4. Donbas war: In April 2014, following the Crimea annexation, Russia-backed separatists seized control of parts of eastern Ukraine's Donbas region, which borders Russia and has a significant Russian-speaking population. The separatists declared two self-proclaimed republics: Donetsk and Luhansk. A bloody war ensued between the Ukrainian forces and the rebels, who received military, financial, and political support from Moscow. Russia denied its direct involvement in the conflict, but evidence showed that it supplied weapons,

⁴⁷ Ukraine crisis: Reasons behind the conflict and here's what's happened... <https://www.businesstoday.in/latest/world/story/ukraine-crisis-reasons-behind-the-conflict-and-heres-whats-happened-so-far-322622-2022-02-15> Accessed on 25th September 2023

⁴⁸ *ibid*

⁴⁹ *ibid*

troops, and mercenaries to the separatists.⁵⁰ The war has killed over 14,000 people and displaced millions more.⁵¹

5. Minsk agreements: In September 2014 and February 2015, under the mediation of France and Germany, Ukraine and Russia signed two peace agreements in Minsk, Belarus, to end the hostilities in Donbas. The agreements called for a ceasefire, a withdrawal of heavy weapons, an exchange of prisoners, a restoration of Ukraine's control over its border with Russia, and a political settlement that would grant special status to Donbas within Ukraine. However, both sides have accused each other of violating the terms of the agreements, and the implementation process has been stalled by mutual distrust and lack of political will.⁵² The conflict remains unresolved and frozen.

The responsibilities and rules of engagement in war are not always respected in the Russia/Ukraine crisis. There have been many reports of violations of IHL and human rights law by both sides of the conflict. Some of the alleged violations include:

1. Indiscriminate attacks on civilian areas, resulting in deaths, injuries, and displacement of thousands of people. For instance, Three people have been killed and at least two injured in an attack on **Beryslav** in Kherson region; attack on Ukraine's southern port of Odesa destroying grain stores;⁵³
2. Torture, ill-treatment, and arbitrary detention of prisoners and captives.⁵⁴
3. Obstruction of humanitarian access and medical assistance to the affected population.⁵⁵

The international community has called for an end to the hostilities and a full respect for the rules of engagement and the law of war. The United Nations Security Council

⁵⁰ *ibid*

⁵¹ *ibid*

⁵² *ibid*

⁵³ Russia-Ukraine war at a glance: what we know on day 579 of the invasion. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/sep/25/russia-ukraine-war-at-a-glance-what-we-know-on-day-579-of-the-invasion>. Accessed on 25th September 2023

⁵⁴ Bogner, M. (2022, November 15). Ukraine / Russia: prisoners of war. United Nations Human Rights. Retrieved April 3, 2024, from <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-briefing-notes/2022/11/ukraine-russia-prisoners-war>

⁵⁵ Ukraine: Humanitarian Access Snapshot (January - June 2023) [EN/UK] - Ukraine. (2023, July 25). ReliefWeb. <https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/ukraine-humanitarian-access-snapshot-january-june-2023-enuk#:~:text=Overall%2C%20access%20to%20the%20people,in%20areas%20under%20Ukrainian%20control.>

has adopted several resolutions on the situation in Ukraine, urging all parties to implement the Minsk agreements, which are aimed at restoring peace and stability in the region. The International Criminal Court (ICC) has also opened a preliminary examination in those the situation in Ukraine, which could lead to a formal investigation and prosecution of responsible for war crimes and crimes against humanity.

5. SANCTIONS TO BE IMPOSED FOR VIOLATION OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW

Over the last half a century, international law has become increasingly involved in the regulation of non-international armed conflict or, as it is known more colloquially, civil war. Non-State actors - like State actors - are increasingly exposed to the threat of accountability and punishment for abuses of human rights. If human rights law has shown itself to be somewhat limited with respect to non-State actors precisely because it is focused on the obligations of the State towards individuals within its jurisdiction, this is not the case when it comes to individual liability for international crimes. The broadening of the scope of the concept of "crimes against humanity" and war crimes in recent years, so as to include acts committed in time of non-international armed conflict, has been of decisive importance in this respect. As the judges at Nuremberg observed in condemning the Nazi leaders for their atrocities: "crimes against international law are committed by men, not by abstract entities, and only by punishing individuals who commit such crimes can the provisions of international law be enforced."⁵⁶

Sanctions are penalties that are imposed for violating a law or a rule. In the context of IHL, sanctions can be applied in different ways. First of all, Sanctions can be imposed by States on civilian internees and prisoners of war who breach the laws, regulations and general orders to which they are subject. These sanctions must respect the principles of legality, necessity, proportionality and humanity, and must not amount to torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. Sanctions can also be imposed by States on individuals who commit grave breaches of IHL, such as war crimes. States have an obligation to prosecute or extradite alleged offenders, and to

⁵⁶ Ibid

cooperate with each other in this regard. Domestic courts and international criminal tribunals can exercise jurisdiction over these crimes. Sanctions can also be imposed by the international community on States or non-State actors who violate IHL or threaten international peace and security. These sanctions can take various forms, such as economic, financial, diplomatic or military measures. The UN Security Council is the main body authorized to impose such sanctions under Chapter VII of the UN Charter.⁵⁷

Sanctions are meant to enforce compliance with IHL and to prevent or end violations. However, they can also have negative humanitarian consequences, especially when they affect the civilian population or the delivery of humanitarian assistance. Therefore, sanctions should be carefully designed and implemented to minimize their adverse impact on humanitarian action.

6. FINDINGS

The research examines the legal issues and challenges arising from the on-going conflict between Russia and Ukraine, which has been described as the worst security crisis in Europe since the end of the Cold War. The research adopts a case study approach that applies the theoretical and empirical knowledge of international law to the specific context and circumstances of the conflict. The research aims to answer the following question: What are the responsibilities and sanctions of international law during armed conflict and occupation, and how are they implemented and enforced in the case of Russia and Ukraine?

The Russian invasion of Ukraine is a clear violation of Article 2 of the United Nations Charter, which prohibits the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state. The recognition of the self-proclaimed "Donetsk People's Republic" and "Luhansk People's Republic" by Russia does not affect the legal status of these territories as part of Ukraine, nor does it justify the use of force by Russia to protect them.

The situation in Eastern Ukraine constitutes an international armed conflict between Ukraine and Russia, as well as a non-international armed conflict between Ukraine and the Russia-backed armed groups. Both parties are bound by the rules of IHL that

⁵⁷ Sanctions | How does law protect in war? - Online casebook. http://casebook.icrc.org/a_to_z/glossary/sanctions. accessed on 26th September 2023

apply to these types of conflicts, such as the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols, as well as customary International Humanitarian Law.

The responsibilities of the parties to the conflict under IHL include respecting and ensuring respect for the principles of distinction, proportionality, and precaution in attack, protecting civilians and civilian objects from harm, providing humanitarian access and assistance to those in need, treating prisoners of war and detainees humanely, and investigating and prosecuting alleged violations of IHL.

The sanctions imposed by the international community on Russia aim to pressure it to comply with IHL and to end its aggression and occupation of Ukraine. These sanctions include among others:

1. United States travel bans and the freezing of U.S. assets, against not-yet-specified individuals who had "asserted governmental authority in the Crimean region without the authorization of the Government of Ukraine" and whose actions were found, *inter alia*, to "undermine democratic processes and institutions in Ukraine".⁵⁸
2. The principal EU sanction "preventing the entry into ... their territories of the natural persons responsible for actions which undermine ... the territorial integrity ... of Ukraine, and of natural persons associated with them, as listed in the Annex".⁵⁹
3. The Central Bank of Russia was blocked from accessing more than \$400 billion in foreign-exchange reserves held abroad.⁶⁰
4. The EU banned all imports of refined oil products from Russia in February 2023 while the UK banned Russian oil imports from December 2022.⁶¹

⁵⁸ Holland, Steve (6 March 2014). "UPDATE 4-Obama warns on Crimea, orders sanctions over Russian moves in Ukraine". *Reuters*. Archived from the original on 18 January 2015. Retrieved 21 January 2015.

⁵⁹ "EU sanctions against Russia over Ukraine crisis". European External Action Service. Archived from the original on 11 June 2015. Retrieved 1 June 2015.

⁶⁰ "The West's Plan to Isolate Putin: Undermine the Ruble". *The New York Times*. 28 February 2022. Archived from the original on 1 March 2022.

⁶¹ "What are the sanctions on Russia and are they hurting its economy?". *BBC News*. 27 January 2022. Retrieved 25 November 2022.

5. Ban on dual-use items, including computer chips, limiting ship-to-ship transactions of sanctioned goods and suspensions of Russian broadcasting licenses in Europe.⁶²

The sanctions include diplomatic, economic, financial, and military measures, such as suspending Russia's membership in international organizations, restricting its access to trade and investment, freezing its assets and imposing travel bans on its officials, and providing military assistance and training to Ukraine.

The research has several implications for both theory and practice. For theory, the research enriches the understanding of the legal aspects and dynamics of armed conflict and occupation, state responsibility, and sanctions in international law. For practice, the research provides useful insights and recommendations for policy makers, practitioners, and stakeholders involved in resolving or preventing similar conflicts in the future.

The sanctions imposed above are they in line with the position of the Law and are they adequate to address the conflict in your own opinion? And if are inadequate, what make them inadequate and what are the better ways of controlling the Conflict?

What are the other Sanctions that may be imposed on Russia and Ukraine for violating IHL –cite the relevant provision of the law

7. CONCLUSION

The responsibilities and sanctions of international law during armed conflict are not always clear or effective. The case study of Russia and Ukraine illustrates the challenges and limitations of applying international law to situations of aggression, occupation, and intervention. The research has shown that both states have violated various norms and principles of international law, such as the prohibition of the use of force, the respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, the protection of human rights and humanitarian law, and the obligation to cooperate with international organizations and mechanisms. However, the responses and reactions of the international community have been largely inadequate and inconsistent, failing to prevent or stop the violations, or to hold the perpetrators accountable. The research

⁶² "European Union countries agree on a new package of sanctions against Russia over the war in Ukraine" (June 21, 2023). *AP*. Accessed 25 June 2023.

has also identified some of the factors that influence the implementation and enforcement of international law, such as political interests, power dynamics, regional alliances, and legal ambiguities.

The research contributes to the existing literature by providing a comprehensive and critical analysis of the legal framework and principles governing armed conflict and occupation, the concept and criteria of state responsibility, and the types and mechanisms of sanctions under international law. The research also evaluates the effectiveness and legitimacy of the sanctions imposed by the international community on Russia, and assesses the challenges and limitations of enforcing them in this case.

The research suggests that there is still need for more effective and coherent action from the international community to uphold and enforce international law during armed conflict. This could include strengthening the role and authority of the United Nations Security Council, enhancing the cooperation and coordination among regional organizations, increasing the pressure and sanctions on the violating states, supporting the peaceful resolution of disputes through dialogue and negotiation, and promoting the respect for human rights and humanitarian law by all parties involved. The research also highlights the importance of addressing the root causes and consequences of armed conflict, such as historical grievances, ethnic tensions, economic inequalities, and humanitarian crises. By doing so, the international community could contribute to the prevention of future conflicts, and to the promotion of peace and security in the region and beyond.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. The parties to the conflict should adhere to their obligations to respect and protect the civilian population and civilian objects, to distinguish between combatants and civilians, and to refrain from indiscriminate or disproportionate attacks.
2. The parties to the conflict should be accountable for any violations of IHL or human rights law that they commit or that they are responsible for. State responsibility entails legal consequences, such as the obligation to cease the wrongful act, to provide reparations to the injured state or individuals, and to cooperate with investigations and prosecutions.

3. The international community should be more active in ensuring compliance with IHL and human rights law, as well as in preventing further escalation of violence and seeking a peaceful resolution of the conflict. The U.N. Security Council, the General Assembly, the Human Rights Council, regional organizations, states, and civil society actors can use various means, such as sanctions, diplomatic pressure, humanitarian assistance, monitoring, reporting, and mediation.
4. The parties to the conflict should respect their obligations under IHL and other applicable legal frameworks, and refrain from any actions that may endanger or harm civilians, civilian objects, or persons hors de combat.
5. The parties to the conflict should cooperate with the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and other humanitarian actors in facilitating their access to the affected areas and populations, and in ensuring the delivery of humanitarian assistance and protection.
6. The parties to the conflict should conduct prompt, impartial and effective investigations into alleged violations of IHL, and prosecute those responsible in accordance with national and international law.
9. There is need to increase the pressure on Russia by imposing more targeted and coordinated sanctions that affect its key sectors and actors, such as energy, banking, defence, technology, and political elites.
10. It is necessary to enhance the support for Ukraine by providing humanitarian assistance, military aid, economic recovery, political reform, and integration into Euro-Atlantic structures.
11. There is need for multilateral negotiations involving all relevant parties, including Russia, Ukraine, the European Union, the United States, NATO, the OSCE (Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe), and other regional actors need to be launched.
12. The root causes of the conflict, such as historical grievances, ethnic tensions, political corruption, economic inequality, human rights violations, and security dilemmas need to be addressed.

13. Promotion of confidence-building measures, such as prisoner exchanges, ceasefire monitoring, humanitarian access, dialogue platforms, civil society initiatives, and cultural exchanges are to be determined.